

 Delete

 Save

 Publish

New upload

Instructions: (i) Upload minimum one file or fill-in required fields (marked with a red star). (ii) Press "Save" to save your upload for editing later. (iii) When ready, press "Publish" to finalize and make your upload public.

Files

 Choose files

 Start upload

Drag and drop files here

– or –

 Choose files

(minimum 1 file required, max 50 GB per dataset - contact us (/support) for larger datasets)

If you're experiencing issues with uploading larger files, read our FAQ section (<https://help.zenodo.org/>) on file upload issues.

Communities

recommended

Specify communities which you wish your upload to appear in. The owner of the community will be notified, and can either accept or reject your request. Please make sure your record complies with the content policy of the communities you add; reported abuse will be followed by account inactivation.

Start typing a community name...

Upload type

required

Publication

Poster

Presentation

Dataset

Image

Video/Audio

Software

Lesson

Physical object

Workflow

Other

Publication type

Journal article ▼

Publication type.

Basic information

required ▼

Digital Object Identifier

e.g. 10.1234/foo.bar

Optional. Did your publisher already assign a DOI to your upload? If not, leave the field empty and we will register a new DOI for you. A DOI allows others to easily and unambiguously cite your upload. Please note that it is NOT possible to edit a Zenodo DOI once it has been registered by us, while it is always possible to edit a custom DOI.

Reserve DOI

Publication date *

2022-07-08

Required. Format: YYYY-MM-DD. In case your upload was already published elsewhere, please use the date of first publication.

Title *

Required.

Authors *

Family name, given names	Affiliation	ORCID (e.g.: 0000-0002-1ξ) ◆ ×
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Optional.

+ Add another author

Description *

<input type="text"/>				
<input type="text"/>	源码	<input type="text"/>		

[Empty input field]

Required.

Version

[Empty input field]

Optional. Mostly relevant for software and dataset uploads. Any string will be accepted, but semantically-versioned tag is recommended.

See semver.org (<http://semver.org>) for more information on semantic versioning.

Language

e.g.: 'eng', 'fr' or 'Polish'

Optional. Primary language of the record. Start by typing the language's common name in English, or its ISO 639 code (two or three-letter code).

See [ISO 639 language codes list](https://www.loc.gov/standards/iso639-2/php/code_list.php) (https://www.loc.gov/standards/iso639-2/php/code_list.php) for more information.

Keywords

[Empty input field]

+ Add another keyword

Additional notes

[Empty text area]

Optional.

License

required

Access right *

- Open Access
- Embargoed Access
- Restricted Access
- Closed Access

Required. Open access uploads have considerably higher visibility on Zenodo.

License *

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

Required. Selected license applies to all of your files displayed on the top of the form. If you want to upload some of your files under different licenses, please do so in separate uploads. If you cannot find the license you're looking for, include a relevant LICENSE file in your record and choose one of the **Other** licenses available (**Other (Open)**, **Other (Attribution)**, etc.). The supported licenses in the list are harvested from opendefinition.org (<https://opendefinition.org>) and spdx.org (<https://spdx.org>). If you think that a license is missing from the list, please contact us (<https://zenodo.org/support>).

Funding
recommended

Zenodo is integrated into reporting lines for research funded by the European Commission via [OpenAIRE](http://www.openaire.eu) (<http://www.openaire.eu>). Specify grants which have funded your research, and we will let your funding agency know!

Grants

European Commission (EU)

Start typing a grant number, name or abbreviation...

Optional. OpenAIRE-supported projects only. For other funding acknowledgements, please use the **Additional Notes** field.
 Note: a human Zenodo curator will need to validate your upload - you may experience a delay before it is available in OpenAIRE.

+ Add another grant

Related/alternate identifiers
recommended

Contributors
optional

References
optional

Journal
optional

Conference
optional

Book/Report/Chapter
optional

Thesis
optional

Subjects
optional

Delete

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Publish

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FAQ

REST API

GitHub

(<http://about.zenodo.org>) (<http://blog.zenodo.org>) (<http://help.zenodo.org>) (<http://developers.zenodo.org>) (<https://github.com/zenodo/zenodo>)

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(<http://help.zenodo.org/features>) (<http://developers.zenodo.org/oai-pmh>) (<http://about.zenodo.org/donate>)

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pmh)

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Contact

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